

Research Article

Unveiling The Therapeutic Potential Of Thiazoles: A Review Of Their Biological Activities

V. S. Anjana*, Rachel Mathew, V. S. Athira, S. R. Anchu

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Mar Dioscorus College Of Pharmacy, Alathara, Thiruvananthapuram.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 31 Oct 2024

Keywords:

Thiazole, Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic, Anti-microbial, Anti-oxidant, Anti-cancer.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14019038

ABSTRACT

Thiazole is a pivotal heterocyclic compound featuring a five-membered ring with sulfur and nitrogen. Thiazole and its derivatives have garnered significant attention in medicinal chemistry due to their diverse biological activities. This review summarizes recent advancements in understanding the pharmacological properties of thiazole derivatives across multiple therapeutic areas. Key biological activities discussed include anti-microbial, anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant activities.

INTRODUCTION

Thiazole is a heterocyclic organic compound characterized by its five-membered ring containing both sulfur and nitrogen atoms. Its chemical formula is C_3H_3NS , and it has gained significant attention due to its diverse biological activities and applications in drug development. Thiazole has a planar, aromatic ring structure with

a sulfur and nitrogen atom adjacent to each other. This ring system imparts unique electronic properties, influencing its reactivity and interaction with biological targets. The electronic distribution and ring tension in thiazole contribute to its ability to form various derivatives with altered biological properties.

Fig 1: 2 D Structure of thiazole

*Corresponding Author: V. S. Anjana

Address: Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Mar Dioscorus College Of Pharmacy, Alathara, Thiruvananthapuram.

Email : anchu2017raj@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

IUPAC name	1,3 – Thiazole
MOLECULAR FORMULA	C3H3NS
MOLECULAR WEIGHT	85.12g/mol
MELTING POINT	-33°C
BOILING POINT	117 °C
SOLUBILITY	Slightly soluble in water Soluble in polar organic solvents

SYNTHESIS OF THIAZOLE [4,5]

Hantzsch thiazole synthesis

Hantzsch thiazole synthesis is one of the most reliable ways of synthesizing thiazoles. It is the

condensation of α -haloaldehydes or ketones with thioureas in neutral, anhydrous solvents to form 2-aminothiazoles.

Similarly, condensation between thiourea and chloroacetaldehyde results in the formation of 2-aminothiazole.

The reaction proceeds through the nucleophilic attack of the nitrogen atom via its lone pair of electrons on the carbon adjacent to the chlorine that is electrophilic (the electrophilicity of the carbon atom is attributed to the -I effect of the chlorine atom), followed by cyclization.

BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES

Anti-inflammatory activity [9]

S.N Thore, Sunil V Gupta, Kamalkishor G. Baheti synthesized thiazole derivatives which exhibited significant analgesic and anti-inflammatory

activities. Among all the synthesized compounds, those possessing 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole2(3H)-thione (compound 11 and compound 14) and pyrazole (compound 15 and compound 16) at position 4 of thiazole (Scheme 2) exhibited more prominent and consistent anti-inflammatory activity than that of the standard drug diclofenac sodium. The compound 9 showed moderate anti-inflammatory activity. The compounds 11 and 14 exhibited good activities in both in silico(docking) and in vivo studies.

Scheme 1 : Synthesis of intermediate 3 and target compound 6

Scheme 2: Synthesis of target compounds 7 – 16

Anti-inflammatory activity was evaluated by the carrageenan-induced paw oedema test in rats (Winter et al., 1962) at equimolar doses equivalent to 25mg/kg (diclofenac sodium) body weight. The anti-inflammatory activity data (Table 1) indicated that all the test compounds protected rats from carrageenan-induced inflammation moderately at

1 h of reaction time with increased activity at 2 h. Decline in activity was observed at 3 h. All the compounds in the series (compound 6 to compound 16) exhibited the anti-inflammatory activity in the range of 14–45 % after 1 h and 21–60 % after 3 h. The compounds 14 and 15 exhibited 44 and 45 % anti-inflammatory

activities, respectively, whereas standard diclofenac sodium showed 40 % activity at 1 h of study. The same compounds showed 55 and 60 % activities at 3 h, whereas standard diclofenac sodium exhibited 55 % activity at 3 h. The

structural correlation with anti-inflammatory activity showed that compounds with 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-one, and pyrazole moiety showed better activity.

Table 1: Results of docking scores and anti-inflammatory activities of title compounds (6-16) against carrageenan-induced rat paw edema model in rats

Compound	Change in paw volume in (ml) after drug treatment (\pm SEM)			Anti-inflammatory activity (% inhibition)			Dock score
	1 h	2 h	3 h	1 h	2 h	3 h	
Control	0.900 \pm 0.03**	1.110 \pm 0.07**	1.200 \pm 0.08**	–	–	–	–
Standard	0.762 \pm 0.04**	0.800 \pm 0.09**	0.850 \pm 0.04**	40.60	56.66	54.92	–
6	0.825 \pm 0.02**	0.885 \pm 0.08**	0.935 \pm 0.01**	30.84	38.07	40.41	–4.088
7	0.842 \pm 0.06**	0.962 \pm 0.07**	1.052 \pm 0.09**	24.24	31.48	26.98	–4.105
8	0.880 \pm 0.08**	1.012 \pm 0.07**	1.105 \pm 0.09**	18.18	25.50	21.42	–4.691
9	0.825 \pm 0.02**	0.885 \pm 0.08**	0.935 \pm 0.01**	34.84	49.07	48.41	–2.602
10	0.844 \pm 0.04**	0.979 \pm 0.06**	1.074 \pm 0.09**	15.15	23.14	19.04	–3.857
11	0.735 \pm 0.04**	0.780 \pm 0.06**	0.840 \pm 0.04**	37.87	53.78	50.79	–4.062
12	0.864 \pm 0.01**	0.995 \pm 0.08**	1.076 \pm 0.08**	14.54	23.51	21.58	–2.075
13	0.787 \pm 0.05**	0.904 \pm 0.07**	0.999 \pm 0.04**	22.72	31.11	25.87	–3.275
14	0.764 \pm 0.04**	0.812 \pm 0.09**	0.862 \pm 0.07**	44.84	57.40	55.55	–3.951
15	0.721 \pm 0.04**	0.740 \pm 0.08**	0.790 \pm 0.05*	45.15	62.96	60.31	–2.952
16	0.851 \pm 0.08**	0.873 \pm 0.07**	0.942 \pm 0.02**	42.12	60.55	55.23	–3.046
Indomethacin							–4.559

Data analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test, ($n = 6$)

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ significant from control

Dose levels: test compounds and diclofenac sodium (25 mg/kg, b.w.p.o.)

Analgesic activity [9,10]

G. Saravanan, V. Alagarsamy, C.R. Prakash, P. Dinesh Kumar and T. Panneer Selvam synthesized a series of thiazole and pyrazole derivatives to study their analgesic effect. According to the literature survey thiazoles were reported to possess anti-microbial, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-tubercular and anti-diuretic

activity. The title compounds (8a to 8j) were synthesized by incorporation of pyrazole moiety at 2nd position of position of 2-hydrazinyl-N-(4-phenylthiazol-2-yl) acetamide (5) by treating with chalcones (7a to 7j). The 2-hydrazinyl-N-(4-phenylthiazol-2-yl) acetamide (5) was synthesized from 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole (3) through 2-chloro-N-(4-phenyl thiazol-2-yl) acetamide (4).

Step 1 : Synthesis of 2-hydrazinyl-N-(4- phenylthiazol-2-yl) acetamide (5).

Step 2 : synthesis of chalcones (7a to 7j)

R = H (8a), 4-OCH₃ (8b), 4-N(CH₃)₂ (8c), 3-NO₂ (8d), 4-CH₃ (8e), 4-OH (8f), 4-Cl (8g), 4-NO₂ (8h),
3,4,5-OCH₃ (8i) and 3-OCH₃-4-OH (8j)

Step 3 : Synthesis of title compounds (8a to 8j)

Table 2: Analgesic activity of title compounds (8a to 8j) by Tail flick method

COMPOUND CODE	DOSE (mg/kg)	PERCENT ANALGESIC ACTIVITY			
		30 min	60 min	120 min	180 min
8a	100	47.43±0.96**	54.25±2.34*	59.87±0.56*	45.68±1.10*
8b	100	36.25±2.11*	49.77±2.61*	56.89±0.63**	47.54±1.16*
8c	100	56.57±0.46**	60.58±1.18***	72.73±0.13*	65.23±0.26*
8d	100	36.46±0.85*	39.59±1.15**	46.24±1.34**	33.51±1.11**
8e	100	46.93±1.11**	59.42±0.48**	63.56±1.26**	55.27±0.38*
8f	100	45.92±1.07*	51.85±0.95*	61.79±2.05**	42.83±1.23**
8g	100	43.54±3.01**	53.73±1.56**	54.51±0.95*	47.36±2.15*
8h	100	39.67±2.24*	51.66±1.18*	55.84±3.28**	36.52±1.19**
8i	100	49.63±2.38*	57.87±0.66**	57.63±0.56*	28.55±0.38*
8j	100	48.82±1.56**	56.53±1.12*	60.14±1.12**	47.74±0.49*
control	-	2±0.33	6±0.48	4±0.60	4±0.87
Pentazocine	10	65.42±0.95**	72.64±0.67***	77.45±1.03***	71.78±0.54*

Each value represents the mean±S.D. (n=6). Significance levels *p<0.5, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 as compared with the respective control

The results of analgesic activity indicate that all the test compounds exhibited significant activity. When compared with standard drug (Pentazocine, 10 mg/kg) the compounds 8c and 8e exhibited comparable analgesic activity at 100 mg/kg. Compounds 8f, 8j, 8a and 8b exhibited moderate analgesic activity. Among the compounds synthesized compound 8d exhibited lowest

analgesic activity. From the above results it may be concluded that compounds containing electron donating groups exhibit better activity than electron withdrawing groups.

Anti-microbial activity [11]

In 2014, Liaras and co-workers synthesized two thiazole-based aminopyrimidine derivatives and eight N-phenylpyrazoline derivatives. Ten

derivatives were tested against 9 g-positive and negative bacteria. The evaluations showed all structures have antibacterial activities. In addition, two compounds (1a and 1b) among all compounds (Table 3) had excellent activity. Streptomycin and ampicillin were used as reference drugs. Most of the derivatives showed comparable or better activities than the reference drugs. Among all derivatives, compound 1a had the best activity. Compound 1b showed the best inhibitory effect against gram-positive bacteria. The best

antibacterial activity against gram-positive and negative bacteria showed by compound 1a. In addition, compound 2d displayed the lowest antibacterial activity, and had no activity against *En. cloacae*. Also, all derivatives had potent activity against *S. aureus* and *L. monocytogenes* compared to streptomycin (except compound 2g). In the case of compounds 2a-h, compounds 2e, 2f and 2h increased the activity in comparison with compound 2a, while compounds 2d and 2g showed the opposite effect.

Table 3: Compounds 1a to 2h

Compound 1a	
Compound 1b	

Compound 2a	
Compound 2b	
Compound 2c	
Compound 2d	
Compound 2e	

Anti-oxidant activity [12]

Vladimir N. Koshelev, Olga V. Primerova, Stepan V. Vorobyev, Anna S. Stupnikova and Ludmila V. Ivanova conducted a study in which a series of thiazoles and thiazolines were synthesized from four thiosemicarbazones with phenol scaffold (Scheme 4). The target compound 1 to compound

5 were prepared as it is shown in Scheme 3 and 4. Initially, the number of thiosemicarbazones was synthesized by the condensation of thiosemicarbazide and series of aldehydes: formylresorcinol-1a; vanillin-1b; 2,3-dihydroxy-4,6-ditert-butylbenzaldehyde-1c; and 4-hydroxy-3,5-di-tert-butylbenzaldehyde-1d.

Scheme 3: Preparation of thiosemicarbazones

Scheme 4: Preparation of thiazoles and thiazolidinones 2-5

Resorcinol derivatives showed a high iron-reducing activity among thiazoles, and alkylated catechol derivatives showed a high iron-reducing activity among thiazolidinones. Thiazolidinones, containing a carboxyl group, showed the greatest activity in both ABTS assay and Feric ion reducing capacity assay. In addition, both types of activity increase with the introduction of the coumarin moiety.

Anti-cancer activity [13,14,15]

Fawziah A. Al-Salmi, Abdulmohsen H. Alrohaimi, Mohammed El Behery, Walaa Megahed, Ola A. Abu Ali, Fahmy G. Elsaid, Eman Fayad, Faten Z. Mohammed and Akaber

T. Keshta developed and designed a safe and efficient anticancer drug, a novel series of thiazole derivatives (compounds 4a-c) and their acetyl derivative (compound 5) were synthesized (Scheme 5) through the reaction of thiosemicarbazone with chloroacetyl chloride, followed by cyclization with boiling ethanol in the presence of fused sodium acetate. Acetyl derivative (compound 5) was obtained via the acetylation of 4a with acetic anhydride. Utilizing elemental analyses and spectroscopic methods (IR and NMR), the structures of the synthesized compounds were verified. Using the MTT assay, all of the synthesized thiazole derivatives

(compounds 4a–c) and compound 5 suppressed the growth of the cancer cell lines MCF-7 and HepG2. Compound 4c was examined in vitro using the VEGFR-2 enzyme assay, cell cycle analysis, and Annexin V FITC/PI assay. Compound 4c

exhibited promising and potential antiproliferative, cell cycle arrest, and apoptosis activation of MCF-7 cancer cell lines compared to the reference drug and MCF-7 control.

Scheme 5: Synthesis of 2-[2-[4-hydroxy-3-substituted benzylidene] hydrazinyl]-thiazole 4[5H]-one derivatives.

In Vitro Cytotoxic Activity against Breast Cancer and Liver Cell Lines (MCF-7 and HepG2)

The MTT assay was used to determine the synthetic compounds' (4a–c) and 5 in vitro cytotoxic activity (IC₅₀): MCF-7 for breast cancer and HepG2 for liver cancer, and Staurosporine (STU) was used as the positive control drug. Their findings revealed that all synthesized thiazole derivatives (4a–c) and 5 exhibited antiproliferative activity of MCF-7 and HepG2 cells compared to the standard drug because of the thiazole moiety in their structure, which contains sulfur and nitrogen. The introduction of different substitutions and

replacements on 2-(4-hydroxybenzylidene) (Scheme 5) may, in turn, increase or decrease the IC₅₀ of the synthesized compounds (4a–c) and 5, as shown in (Table 4). Consequently, compound 4c, which contains a substitution on 2-(4-hydroxybenzylidene) (R=NH=NH-Ph), showed efficient cytotoxic activity toward MCF-7 and HepG2, with IC₅₀ values 2.57 ± 0.16 μM and 7.26 ± 0.44 μM, respectively, followed by 12.7 ± 0.77 μM and 6.69 ± 0.41 μM, respectively, for compound 4a, which does not contain any substitutions on 2-(4-hydroxybenzylidene) (R=H) compared to 6.77 ± 0.41 μM and 8.4 ± 0.51 μM, respectively, of the standard drug.

Table 4 : In vitro cytotoxic activity (IC₅₀) of thiazole derivatives (4a–c) and 5 in the MCF-7 and HepG2 cancer cell lines when compared to STU.

IC ₅₀ Values (μM) of Compounds	MCF-7	HepG2
4a	12.7 ± 0.77	6.69 ± 0.41
4b	31.5 ± 1.91	51.7 ± 3.13
4c	2.57 ± 0.16	7.26 ± 0.44
5	28.0 ± 1.69	26.8 ± 1.62
Staurosporine	6.77 ± 0.41	8.4 ± 0.51

VEGFR-2 inhibitory activity

The ability of compound 4c to inhibit VEGFR-2, a trans-membrane tyrosine kinase receptor that promotes tumor angiogenesis, growth, and proliferation was investigated. It is necessary to comprehend the mode of operation of synthetic thiazole derivatives and their capacity to cause cancer cell death. Sorafenib, a popular VEGFR-2

inhibitor, served as the positive control in the experiment. The outcomes demonstrated that compound 4c was somewhat effective at inhibiting the VEGFR-2 enzyme (IC₅₀ = 0.15 μM) compared to Sorafenib (IC₅₀ = 0.059 μM) (Table 2). This result confirms the cytotoxic capacity of compound 4c to arrest cancer cell growth and division.

Table 5: VEGFR-2 inhibitory activity in vitro of compound 4c compared to Sorafenib.

Compounds	VEGFR-2 IC ₅₀ Values (μM)
4c	0.15
Sorafenib	0.059

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The review highlights that thiazole derivatives exhibit a range of beneficial biological activities, including anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, anti-oxidant, and analgesic effects. This indicates a promising avenue for future research. The development of thiazole derivatives with these properties suggests they could provide effective and selective therapeutic options with fewer unwanted side effects.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors are thankful to MAR DIOSCORUS COLLEGE OF PHARAMCY management, Thiruvananthapuram, for providing all facilities for the present investigation.

REFERENCE

1. Adile Ayati, Saeed Emami, Ali Asadipour, Abbas Shafiee, Alireza Foroumadi. Recent applications of 1,3-thiazole core structure in the identification of new lead compounds and drug discovery. *The European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2015, 97, 699-718.
2. Shelly Pathania, Raj Kumar Narang, Ravindra K. Rawal. Role of sulphur-heterocycles in medicinal chemistry: An update. *The European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2019, 180, 486-508
3. AyaE Ghonim, Alessia Ligrest, Alessandro Rabbito, AliMokhtar Mahmoud, Vincenzo Di Marzo, Noha A. Osman, Ashraf H. Abadi. Structure-activity relationships of thiazole and benzothiazole derivatives as selective cannabinoid CB2 agonists with in vivo anti-inflammatory properties. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2019, 180, 154-17
4. Renata Paprocka, Malgorzata Wiese, Andrzej Eljaszewicz, Anna Helmin-Basa, Andrzej Gzella, Bozena Modzelewska-Banachiewicz, Jacek Michalkiewicz. Synthesis and anti-inflammatory activity of new 1,2,4-triazole derivatives. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters* 2015, 25, 13, s 2664-2667.
5. Mahajan NS, Pattan SR, Jadhav RL, Pimpodkar NV and Manikrao AM. Synthesis of some thiazole compounds of biological interest containing mercapto group, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2008, 6, 800-806.

6. Dakeshwar Kumar Verma, Yeestdev Dewangan and Chandrabhan Verma, Chapter 4 - Reactions of heterocyclic compounds. Handbook of Organic Name Reactions, 2023, 269-298.
7. Chandra Bhushan Mishra, Shikha Kumari, Manisha Tiwari . Thiazole- A promising heterocycle for the development of potent CNS active agents , European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry 2015 ,92 , 1 -34.
8. Dakeshwar Kumar Verma, Yeestdev Dewangan and Chandrabhan Verma . Handbook of Organic Named Reactions: Reagents, Mechanisms and Applications , 2023 ,269-298.
9. S.N Thore , Sunil V Gupta, Kamalkishor G. Baheti .Synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of 5-methyl-2-phenylthiazole-4-substituted heteroazoles as a potential anti-inflammatory and analgesic agents , Journal of Saudi Chemical Society , 2016 , 20, P S46-S52.
10. G. Saravanan , V. Alagarsamy , C.R. Prakash, P. Dinesh Kumar and T. Panneer Selvam. Synthesis of Novel Thiazole Derivatives as Analgesic Agents, Asian J. Res. Pharm. Sci. 2011; 1: 4, 134-138
11. Seyedmohammad Hosseinezhad, Ali Ramazani . Thiazole ring- the antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer active scaffold, Arabian Journal of Chemistry, 2023, 16,11, 105234.
12. Keshav B. Gangurde , Vishnu A. Adole , Dattatray S. Ghotekar. Computational study: Synthesis, spectroscopic (UV-vis, IR, NMR), antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant, molecular docking and ADME of new (E)-5-(1-(2-(4-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)thiazol-2-yl)hydrazineylidene)ethyl)-2,4-dimethylthiazole, Results in Chemistry, 2023,6,101093
13. Lemilemu F, Bitew M, Demissie TB, Eswaramoorthy R, Endale M. Synthesis, antibacterial and antioxidant activities of Thiazole-based Schiff base derivatives: a combined experimental and computational study, BMC Chem. 2021;15(1): 1– 18
14. PrabodhChander Sharma, KushalKumar Bansal, Archana Sharma, Diksha Sharma, Aakash Deep, Thiazole-containing compounds as therapeutic targets for cancer therapy, European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry, 2020, 188, 112016.
16. Haifeng He , Xiaoyan Wang, Liqiao Shi Wenyan Yin, Ziwen Yang, Hongwu He, Ying Liang. Synthesis, antitumor activity and mechanism of action of novel 1,3-thiazole derivatives containing hydrazide-hydrazone and carboxamide moiety, Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters , 2016, 26,14,3263-3270.
17. Nancy Y. Guerrero-Pepinosa , María C. Cardona-Trujillo , Sandra C. Garzón-Castaño , Luz Angela Veloza , Juan C. Sepúlveda-Arias . Antiproliferative activity of thiazole and oxazole derivatives: A systematic review of in vitro and in vivo studies, Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy, 2021,138, 111495

HOW TO CITE: V. S. Anjana, Rachel Mathew, V. S. Athira, S. R. Anchu , Unveiling The Therapeutic Potential Of Thiazoles: A Review Of Their Biological Activities, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 10, 1860-1871. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14019038>

